

Züri Can Study

Dropout Analysis 2023-2025

Document Information

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Definitions.....	3
3. Methods - Dropout and annual dropout rate.....	3
4. Results.....	4
4.1. Group Differences.....	5
4.2. Comparison of group differences using different methods of estimation	7
4.3. Multivariate stepped exponential model estimates	9

1. Introduction

The validity of a study depends, among other things, on how many participants remain enrolled throughout its duration. High dropout rates undermine the reliability of its findings. Participants may leave for various reasons: some may lose interest, others may need to be excluded because they no longer meet the inclusion criteria. These categories can also overlap — a participant who has lost interest may ultimately be excluded because they no longer meet the inclusion criteria.

A dropout analysis establishes what proportion of participants withdrew or were excluded before completing the study, and identifies factors associated with dropout. In an ongoing longitudinal study, any such analysis is necessarily preliminary.

2. Definitions

Calculating the dropout rate requires clear definitions of enrolment and dropout. We defined the enrolment date as the date on which a participant received their study ID and thus became eligible to purchase study cannabis. Dropout was defined as the date on which eligibility to purchase study cannabis ceased. Temporary suspensions from purchasing study cannabis, for example due to pending medical evaluation, were not counted as dropout.

3. Methods - Dropout and annual dropout rate¹

The simplest calculation of the dropout **D** up to a reference date divides the number of participants **N_E** who have left the study by the total number ever enrolled **N**. This can be expressed as a percentage: $D = N_E / N * 100$.

As of December 31, 2025, the cumulative dropout rate was 20.6% ($638 / 3,102 \times 100$). At that point, the study had been running for just over two years. The annual dropout rate **D_a** could therefore be estimated at 10% ($20.6\% / 2 \approx 10\%$). However, this would only be accurate, if all participants had enrolled simultaneously. This is not the case due to Züri Can's rolling inclusion process. For instance, some social clubs began participant recruitment late due to difficulties in finding a suitable location.

Meaningful comparisons across pharmacies, social clubs, and the DIZ therefore require accounting for each participant's time in the study. A participant who joined the study one week before the reference date is far less likely to have dropped out compared to one who joined two years earlier. A standard tool for this type of analysis is survival analysis. There

¹ For detailed information on the analysis, including the syntax for running a simulation, see Nordt, C. (2026). Syntax - Stepped Exponential Survival Analysis (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20413691>

are two main options for this analysis: The first option is the Kaplan-Meier method, which is semiparametric and makes no assumptions about how dropout is distributed over time and focuses on the differences between groups. The second option are parametric models that make assumptions about how dropout is distributed. A parametric model with an exponential distribution, for instance, assumes a constant dropout rate. For such a model, a fixed value for the annual dropout rate can be derived directly from the estimates of the statistical model.

Both the semiparametric and the parametric survival analysis require an indicator for each participant that indicates whether they were still eligible to purchase study cannabis as of the reference date. For this purpose, we used the variable **c** for “censored” (1 = still eligible to purchase; 0 = no longer eligible to purchase).

To indicate how long the person participated in the study, we use the variable **t**, which denotes the duration of participation in years. For example, Person A became eligible to purchase study cannabis two years ago (**t** = 2.0) and still is eligible (**c** = 1). Person B also joined two years ago but left the study after just one year (**t** = 1.0, **c** = 0). The value for **t** is calculated to the exact day (= days / 365.25). Depending on the software used, care must be taken to ensure that **t** is not zero.

4. Results

Among the 638 individuals who dropped out (i.e. the uncensored cases), the time **t** from enrolment to dropout ranged from 1 day to 789 days. Among the 2,464 participants who did not drop out (i.e. the censored cases), **t** from enrolment to the reference date (December 31, 2025) ranged from 9 days to 864 days.

Figure 1 shows the observed proportion of participants eligible to purchase study cannabis over time (Kaplan-Meier curve with confidence interval) as a blue line. In two out of three cases (64.7%), the reason for dropout was failure to complete the bi-annual online survey. Under a standard exponential model (green line), the estimated annual dropout rate is 13.4% (95% CI: 12.4%–14.5%).

Dropout due to non-completion of the recurring online survey does not occur at a constant rate over time; rather, it appears as a ‘step effect’. The red line represents a stepped exponential model adapted to capture this pattern. It estimates that 67.6% (95% CI: 64.0% – 71.1%) of dropouts were due to not completed surveys and places the annual dropout rate at 15.0% (95% CI: 13.9% – 16.2%). The stepped model fits the observed data substantially better than the standard exponential model and reflects the proportion of dropouts due to non-completion quite well. Therefore, we considered the stepped exponential model to be the most accurate method. This is relevant because the standard exponential (green line) model estimates a dropout rate that is around 11% lower.

Figure 1: Trends of dropout rates among participants eligible to purchase study cannabis

Kaplan-Meier-Survival Analysis, standard- and stepped Exponential-Model; Data from July 2023 until December 2025

4.1. Group Differences

Dropout rates may vary by point of sale type and by participant characteristics. In survival models, group differences are expressed as hazard ratios (**HRs**), indicating whether dropout is more or less likely in one group relative to a reference group. In logistic models, which do not account for individual participation time, odds ratios (**ORs**) serve the same purpose. Under the exponential survival model used here, **HRs** and **ORs** are directly comparable.

Group membership was based on each participant's mean value across all available surveys, rather than assuming characteristics remained fixed throughout the study. It would not be correct, for instance, to assume that participants maintain the same frequency of cannabis use over the whole duration of the study.

Figure 2: Trends of dropout rates among participants eligible to purchase study cannabis by type of points of sale

Stepped Exponential-Model; Data from July 2023 until December 2025

Dropout trends differed clearly across point-of-sale types (Figure 2). Social clubs showed roughly 50% higher dropout than pharmacies (red line; HR = 1.52; 95% CI = 1.27–1.77). There is no significant difference in the dropout rates between pharmacies (blue line) and the DIZ (green line) over time.

The stepped exponential model shows that most participants drop out of the study because they fail to complete the online survey on time. This proportion is noticeably higher at pharmacies (around 84%) and the DIZ (around 80%) than at social clubs (around 56%). One possible explanation is that some social clubs more actively manage their participants' participation status than other points of sale.

Across participant characteristics, the role of survey non-completion as a reason for dropout was broadly consistent. The only exception is ADHD: Participants with ADHD had roughly twice the overall dropout risk (OR = 1.96; 95% CI = 1.26 – 2.65) and around four times the risk of dropping out specifically due to not completing the survey (OR = 4.38; 95% CI = 0.40 – 8.37). Among those who dropped out, survey non-completion accounted

for around 89% of cases in participants with ADHD, compared with around 65% in those without.

4.2. Comparison of group differences using different methods of estimation

Table 1 summarises the univariate results for group differences across the two described methods. Statistically significant effects are highlighted in bold. The only difference between the two methods concerns the gender effect for women compared to men [**OR** = 1.20 (0.97 - 1.48) versus **HR = 1.29 (1.05 - 1.54)**].

Among demographic variables, age, education, employment status, and income were the strongest predictors of dropout. Participants aged 18–25 years were about twice as likely to drop out as those aged 26–35, while those aged 36–45 and 46–80 had roughly half the dropout risk of the reference group (26–35).

Participants with a university degree, were each about half as likely to drop out compared to participants without a university degree. Participants with a monthly income above CHF 4,500, were about half as likely to drop out as participants with a lower income. Unemployed participants were nearly twice as likely to drop out compared to those in employment.

Frequency of cannabis use was not significantly associated with dropout risk.

Among health-related variables, ADHD, depression, anxiety disorder, sleep problems, and somatic problems were associated with an increased dropout risk while chronic illness and recent healthcare use were not.

Table 1: Results for analysis of group differences (univariate)

	Dropout	
	OR (CI 95%)	HR (CI 95%)
Gender (male as reference)		
Female	1.20 (0.97 - 1.48)	1.29 (1.05 - 1.54)
Non-binary	0.63 (0.24 - 1.63)	0.63 (0.06 - 1.21)
Age category (26-35 years as reference)		
18-25 years	2.12 (1.66 - 2.70)	2.11 (1.68 - 2.54)
36-45 years	0.49 (0.38 - 0.63)	0.49 (0.38 - 0.61)
46-80 years	0.51 (0.38 - 0.67)	0.51 (0.38 - 0.65)
University degree	0.50 (0.42 - 0.61)	0.54 (0.45 - 0.63)
Not employed	1.88 (1.44 - 2.45)	1.81 (1.39 - 2.23)
Income more than 4500 CHF per month	0.49 (0.41 - 0.60)	0.50 (0.42 - 0.59)
Swiss citizenship	0.87 (0.71 - 1.06)	0.84 (0.69 - 0.99)
(Almost) daily cannabis use	1.21 (0.99 - 1.48)	1.13 (0.92 - 1.34)
ADHD	1.85 (1.24 - 2.75)	1.96 (1.26 - 2.65)
Depression	2.77 (1.51 - 5.07)	2.56 (1.21 - 3.92)
Anxiety disorder	4.67 (2.13 - 10.23)	4.63 (1.72 - 7.55)
Sleep problems	1.50 (1.17 - 1.92)	1.64 (1.26 - 2.02)
Somatic problems	2.12 (1.40 - 3.23)	2.33 (1.43 - 3.23)
Chronic illness	1.11 (0.82 - 1.50)	0.99 (0.71 - 1.26)
Medical consultation within past 6 months	0.94 (0.73 - 1.20)	0.88 (0.67 - 1.10)
Type of points of sale (Pharmacies as reference)		
Social clubs	1.46 (1.22 - 1.75)	1.52 (1.27 - 1.77)
DIZ	1.41 (0.87 - 2.26)	1.02 (0.59 - 1.45)

Data from July 2023 until December 2025; Odds Ratios (OR) estimated with logistic model; Hazard Ratios (HR) estimated with stepped Exponential-Model; CHF = Swiss Francs; ADHD = attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder; DIZ = Drug Information Center

4.3. Multivariate stepped exponential model estimates

The effects of individual factors presented in .

Table 1 were estimated in isolation (technically, the term ‘univariate’ is used for this). Univariate estimates treat each predictor independently and do not account for correlations between variables — for instance, between different mental health indicators. A multivariate model addresses this by identifying which combination of variables best predicts dropout.

We used a backwards elimination procedure: all variables significant in univariate analysis were entered into a multivariate stepped exponential model, and the variable with the highest p-value was removed at each step until only those with $p < 0.05$ remained. Table 2 presents estimated values for the multivariate model (hierarchical exponential model), alongside the univariate values from .

Table 1 for comparison.

Age, education, and income remained significant in the multivariate model, though effect sizes were generally smaller. The age effects for the 36–45 and 46–80 age groups remained very similar. Anxiety and sleep problems remained significant predictors in the multivariate model, with smaller effects than in the univariate model. The elevated dropout risk at social clubs relative to pharmacies remained significant but was reduced.

The fourfold increased risk of survey-related dropout among participants with ADHD was largely unchanged in the multivariate model (HR = 3.84; 95% CI: 0.12 – 7.57). Both models confirmed that the share of dropout due to non-completion of the survey was significantly lower at social clubs than at pharmacies (univariate: OR = 0.25 [0.17–0.36]; multivariate: OR = 0.26 [0.16–0.36]).

Table 2: Results for analysis of group differences (univariate and multivariate)

	Dropout	
	Univariate HR (CI 95%)	Multivariate HR (CI 95%)
Gender (male as reference)		
Female	1.29 (1.05- 1.54)	ns
Non-binary	0.63 (0.06 - 1.21)	ns
Age category (26-35 years as reference)		
18-25 years	2.11 (1.68 - 2.54)	1.57 (1.22 - 1.92)
36-45 years	0.49 (0.38 - 0.61)	0.55 (0.42 - 0.68)
46-80 years	0.51 (0.38 - 0.65)	0.51 (0.38 - 0.65)
University degree	0.54 (0.45 - 0.63)	0.68 (0.56 - 0.80)
Not employed	1.81 (1.39 - 2.23)	1.33 (0.97 - 1.70)
Income higher than 4500 CHF per month	0.50 (0.42 - 0.59)	0.81 (0.64 - 0.97)
Swiss citizenship	0.84 (0.69 - 0.99)	ns
(Almost) daily cannabis use	1.13 (0.92 - 1.34)	ns
ADHD	1.96 (1.26 - 2.65)	ns
Depression	2.56 (1.21 - 3.92)	ns
Anxiety disorder	4.63 (1.72 - 7.55)	2.93 (0.92 - 4.94)
Sleep problems	1.64 (1.26 - 2.02)	1.33 (1.00 - 1.65)
Somatic problems	2.33 (1.43 - 3.23)	ns
Chronic illness	0.99 (0.71 - 1.26)	ns
Medical consultation within past 6 months	0.88 (0.67 - 1.10)	ns
Type of points of sale (Pharmacies as reference)		
Social clubs	1.52 (1.27 - 1.77)	1.38 (1.15 - 1.60)
DIZ	1.02 (0.59 - 1.45)	ns

Data from July 2023 until December 2025; 'ns' not included in final multivariate model; Hazard Ratios (HR) estimated with stepped Exponential-Model; CHF = Swiss Francs; ADHD = attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder; DIZ = Drug Information Center